

SROC III

Third Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

**November, 2-3rd 2024,
Ethno Complex Vrdnicka kula, Vrdnik**

ADT should systematically added to pelvis radiotherapy in unfavorable intermediate risk prostate cancer – yes

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13988747

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Prostate cancer remains the fourth most common cancer in men worldwide. Intermediate-risk prostate cancer (IR-PCa), characterized by specific clinical and pathological features such as T2b or T2c staging, Gleason Score (GS) of 7, and PSA levels between 10-20 ng/mL, is a heterogeneous disease. It can be divided into favorable (FIR) and unfavorable intermediate-risk (UIR) groups based on factors such as GS, number of biopsy cores involved, and recurrence rates. Patients with UIR-PCa have higher risks of recurrence and prostate cancer-specific mortality (PCSM) compared to FIR patients. Current NCCN guidelines recommend several treatment approaches for UIR-PCa, including radical prostatectomy, external beam radiotherapy (EBRT) with androgen deprivation therapy (ADT), or a combination of EBRT with brachytherapy. Despite advances in radiotherapy, the role of ADT in UIR-PCa remains controversial, particularly in the context of dose-escalated radiotherapy (DERT) and hypofractionated regimens. However, multiple studies, including the MARCAP meta-analysis and RTOG 9408 trial, suggest that the addition of ADT to radiation therapy improves metastasis-free survival and reduces PCSM in UIR-PCa patients. Pelvic nodal radiotherapy (PNRT) has also been debated, with conflicting results from studies like GETUG-01 and RTOG 9413. Recent trials, including the POP-RT trial, have demonstrated improved outcomes in high-risk PCa with the use of whole pelvic radiotherapy (WPRT) and ADT. However, there is limited data on the benefits of WPRT in UIR-PCa. In conclusion, while evidence supports the addition of ADT to radiotherapy in UIR-PCa, further research is needed to establish the role of WPRT and refine treatment strategies for this population. Thus, the recommendation

to systematically add ADT to radiotherapy in UIR-PCa, though supported, remains cautiously optimistic.

Keywords: prostate cancer, unfavorable intermediate-risk (UIR), androgen deprivation therapy (ADT), external beam radiotherapy (EBRT), whole pelvic radiotherapy (WPRT)

**SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress
2024**

Urednik
Olivera Ivanov

Izdavač
Institut za Onkologiju Vojvodine

Grafička priprema i štampa
NS digiprint, Novi Sad

Tiraž
200

ISBN 978-86-82113-16-4

CIP – Каталогизacija у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

616-006(048.3)

SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress (3 ; 2024 ; Vrdnik)

Abstract book / Third Serbian Radiation Oncology
Congress, SROC III, November, 2nd-3rd 2024, Ethno Complex
Vrdnicka Kula, Vrdnik ; [urednik Olivera Ivanov]. – Novi
Sad : Institut za onkologiju Vojvodine, 2024 (Novi Sad : NS
digiprint). – 60 str. ; 21 cm

Tiraž 200. – Str. 3: Introduction / Olivera Ivanov.

ISBN 978-86-82113-16-4

a) Онкологија – Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 155485193